

1 Plášil *et al.* Theuerdankite, a new silver mineral

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3 **Theuerdankite, Ag₃AsO₄, a new mineral from Alter Theuerdank Mine (St.**
4 **Andreasberg), Germany**

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21
22 **Abstract**

23 The new mineral theuerdankite, ideally Ag₃AsO₄, was found in the Alter Theuerdank Mine,
24 Beerberg, St. Andreasberg, Goslar District, Lower Saxony, Germany. Theuerdankite occurs
25 as aggregates of anhedral grains up to 3 mm in size, growing in cavities of strongly
26 supergene-weathered material consisting of native silver and chlorargyrite. It is dark violet,
27 changing to reddish and black when exposed to the air and light. It has a grey to violet grey
28 streak; when readily fresh, its streak is brownish-red. The Mohs hardness is about 2. It is
29 brittle without any observable cleavage or parting and with a conchoidal fracture. The
30 calculated density is 6.622 g·cm⁻³. In reflected light, theuerdankite is dark grey with pinkish
31 tint, without any observable bireflectance, pleochroism, or anisotropy. It shows dark red
32 internal reflections. The reflectance values for wavelengths recommended by the Commission
33 on Ore Mineralogy of the IMA are (R %): 13.3 (470 nm), 12.8 (546 nm), 12.7 (589 nm), 12.5
34 (650 nm). The empirical formula (based on 4 *apfu*) are Ag_{3.00}As_{1.00}O₄. Theuerdankite is cubic,
35 space group *P*-43*n*, *a* = 6.144(2) Å, *V* = 231.93(13) Å³ and *Z* = 2. The six strongest X-ray
36 powder diffraction lines are [*d*_{obs} in Å, (*I*), *hkl*]: 3.0736, (22), 200; 2.7502, (100), 210; 2.5106,
37 (55), 211; 1.7050, (36), 320; 1.6249, (44), 321; 1.3412, (17), 421. The crystal structure of
38 theuerdankite (*R*₁ = 1.69% for 519 reflections having *I* > 3σ(*I*)), is isotypic to those of
39 synthetic Ag₃AsO₄ and Ag₃PO₄. The Gram-Charlier development describing the higher-order
40 tensors representing the atomic displacement parameters of the silver atom was implemented,
41 documenting that silver tends to behave in theuerdankite structure anharmonically at room
42 temperature.

44 **Keywords:** theuerdankite, new mineral, silver minerals, crystal structure, Gram-Charlier
45 development, goodness-of-fit, St. Andreasberg

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47

48 **Introduction**

49 Theuerdankite, ideally Ag_3AsO_4 , is a new silver mineral from the famous historic mining
50 region of St. Andreasberg in Lower Saxony, Germany. It is named after the type locality, the
51 Alter Theuerdank Mine. The new mineral and its name have been approved by the
52 Commission on New Minerals, Nomenclature and Classification of the International
53 Mineralogical Association (IMA 2023-009). The holotype specimen (polished section) of
54 theuerdankite is deposited in the collections of the Department of Mineralogy and Petrology,
55 National Museum in Prague, Cirkusová 1740, 193 00 Prague 9, Czech Republic under the
56 catalog number PIP 59/2022. Here, we report on its description, including crystal structure
57 refinement using a Gram-Charlier development describing the thermal movement of the silver
58 atom in the crystal structure, which vibrates anharmonically around its equilibrium position.
59 We also append a discussion on the proper handling of the diffraction data and the refinement.

60

61 **Occurrence**

62 Theuerdankite was found on a specimen originating from the Alter Theuerdank Mine,
63 Beerberg, St Andreasberg, Braunlage, Goslar District, Lower Saxony, Germany (51° 42' 29"
64 N, 10° 31' 41" E). This mine is among the important mines in the St. Andreasberg mining
65 district and it is famous for the rich findings of the so-called “*buttermilch-erz*” = ore
66 consisting of chlorargyrite. We refer to the paper by Schnorrer et al. (2009) for details on the
67 occurrence and geology. Associated minerals within the studied specimen are chlorargyrite,
68 native silver and calcite. Theuerdankite is most probably of supergene origin but could also be
69 late hydrothermal if these fluids were oxidizing enough to convert As in the primary minerals
70 to arsenates.

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72 **Physical and optical properties**

73 Theuerdankite occurs as irregular aggregates up to 3 mm in size (Fig. 1), growing in cavities
74 of strongly supergene-weathered material consisting of native silver and chlorargyrite. Its
75 color is dark violet, changing to reddish and black when exposed to the air. It darkens when
76 exposed to light. It has a grey to violet grey streak; when fresh, its streak is brownish-red. It is
77 non-fluorescent in SW and LW ultraviolet light. The Mohs hardness is estimated at about 2
78 based on scratch tests. Theuerdankite is brittle; no cleavage and no parting were observed.
79 The fracture is conchoidal. A density of $6.622 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ was calculated using the ideal formula
80 and unit-cell volume refined from the single-crystal XRD data; $6.620 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ for the empirical
81 formula (WDS). Theuerdankite is dark grey with pinkish tints in reflected light with no
82 visible bireflectance and no pleochroism; no anisotropy has been observed. There are dark red
83 internal reflections, visible around fractures and inclusions of native silver (Fig. 2).
84 Reflectance values measured in the air using a spectrophotometer MSP400 Tidas at Leica
85 microscope, with a 20× objective, are given in Table 1 and shown in Figure 3.

86

87 **Chemical composition**

88 Quantitative chemical analyses were carried out using a Cameca SX100 electron microprobe
89 (WDS mode, 15 kV, 5 nA, 10 μm beam diameter) at the National Museum Prague, Czech
90 Republic. The following standards and X-ray lines were used to minimize line overlaps: Ag
91 ($\text{AgL}\alpha$), chalcopyrite ($\text{CuK}\alpha$), clinoclase ($\text{AsL}\alpha$) and fluorapatite ($\text{PK}\alpha$). Peak counting times
92 were 20 s for all elements and 10 s for each background. The results obtained (average of 16
93 spot analyses) are given in Table 2. Contents of other elements with atomic numbers higher
94 than that of carbon are below detection limits. Matrix correction by PAP software (Pouchou
95 and Pichoir, 1985) was applied to the data. The calculated empirical formula of theuerdankite
96 based on 4 *apfu* and 4 O atoms is $\text{Ag}_{3.00}\text{As}_{1.00}\text{O}_4$. The ideal formula for theuerdankite is
97 Ag_3AsO_4 , which requires Ag_2O 75.15 and As_2O_5 24.85, a total of 100.00 wt.%. It is soluble in
98 an ammonia solution 25% and decomposes when heated up in a melting point tube without
99 the evolution of H_2O .

100

101 **Raman spectroscopy**

102 The Raman spectra of theuerdankite were collected in the range 50-4000 cm^{-1} using a DXR
103 dispersive Raman Spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) mounted on a confocal Olympus
104 microscope. The Raman signal was excited by an unpolarised green 532 nm solid state, diode-
105 pumped laser and detected by a CCD detector. The experimental parameters were: 100 \times
106 objective, 10 s exposure time, 100 exposures, 50 μm slit spectrograph aperture and 1 mW
107 laser power level. The eventual thermal damage of the measured points was excluded by
108 visual inspection of the excited surface after measurement, observation of possible decay of
109 spectral features at the start of excitation, and checking for a thermal downshift of Raman
110 lines. The instrument was set up using a software-controlled calibration procedure using
111 multiple neon emission lines (wavelength calibration), multiple polystyrene Raman bands
112 (laser frequency calibration), and standardized white-light sources (intensity calibration).
113 Spectral manipulations were performed using the Omnic 9 software (Thermo Scientific).

114 The Raman spectrum of theuerdankite is given in Figure 4. The main bands observed
115 are (in wavenumbers): 816, 787, 408, 337, and 82 cm^{-1} . The most prominent very strong
116 Raman band at 787 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 816 cm^{-1} is attributed to overlapping ν_1 (AsO_4)³⁻
117 symmetric stretching and ν_3 (AsO_4)³⁻ antisymmetric stretching vibrations. Raman band 408
118 cm^{-1} is attributed to the ν_4 (AsO_4)³⁻ bending vibration. Raman band at 337 cm^{-1} is related to
119 the ν_2 (AsO_4)³⁻ bending vibrations and those below 200 cm^{-1} to lattice modes (Vansant *et al.*,
120 1973; Nakamoto, 2009; Frost *et al.*, 2010; Čejka *et al.*, 2011). The observed bands are
121 comparable to those in the infrared absorption spectrum of the synthetic Ag_3AsO_4 - 825, 785,
122 405 and 330 cm^{-1} (Hájek *et al.*, 1979; Muck *et al.*, 1980).

123

124 **X-ray crystallography and structure refinement**

125 X-ray powder diffraction data of theuerdankite were obtained using a pseudo-Gandolfi scan
126 on XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system equipped with the HyPix-Arc150 detector, using
127 monochromatic $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation from the microfocus rotating anode. The positions and
128 intensities of diffractions were found and refined using the Pearson VII profile-shape function
129 of the ZDS program package (Ondruš, 1993). The unit-cell parameters were refined by the
130 least-squares program of Burnham (1962). The X-ray powder diffraction data of

131 theuerdankite are given in Table 3. The refined unit-cell parameter (for the space group $P-43n$) is $a = 6.1448(3) \text{ \AA}$, $V = 231.01(2) \text{ \AA}^3$ and $Z = 2$.

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133 Single-crystal X-ray diffraction data for theuerdankite were collected on XtaLAB
134 Synergy, DW system equipped with the HyPix-Arc150 detector, using monochromatic $\text{MoK}\alpha$
135 radiation from the microfocus rotating anode from the same crystal as powder XRD data were
136 collected. A fragment of the single crystal with approximate dimensions $85 \times 48 \times 28 \text{ \mu m}^3$
137 was mounted on a glass fiber and analyzed. The complete data set (100% to the resolution of
138 0.4 \AA) of the high-redundancy (>6) was collected using ω -scans (frame width of 0.5° and a
139 counting time of 4 seconds per frame). Data reduction was performed using CrysAlisPro
140 Version 1.171.43.111 (Rigaku, 2024). The data were corrected for Lorentz factor and
141 absorption (multi-scan, ABSPACK scaling algorithm; Rigaku, 2024).

142 The structure of theuerdankite was solved from the intensity data using the intrinsic
143 phasing by SHELXT program (Sheldrick, 2015) and refined using the software Jana2020
144 (Petříček *et al.*, 2023). The structure was refined as an inversion twin, and extinction
145 (isotropic; Becker and Coppens, 1974) was also refined during the final stages of the
146 refinement (Table 4). We used the third-order anharmonic Gram–Charlier development (see
147 for instance Volkov *et al.*, 2023) to describe the Debye–Waller factors for the Ag atoms,
148 which improved the refinement considerably (see the Discussion). Refinement details are
149 given in Table 4, atomic parameters (including atomic displacement parameters (ADP) and
150 bond-valence sums calculated using parameters reported by Gagné and Hawthorne, 2015) are
151 given in Table 5; the coefficients of the third-order Gram–Charlier development are given in
152 crystallographic information file (cif); selected interatomic distances are reported in Table 6.
153 The Vesta program (Momma and Izumi, 2011) was used to plot the electron density and the
154 isosurface for ADPs of silver atoms.

155 The structure of theuerdenkite contains AsO_4 tetrahedra (Table 5) whose centers lie on
156 lattice points of a $b.c.c.$ lattice. The Ag1 atom occupies the $6c$ Wyckoff position, surrounded
157 by four O atoms at a distance of $2.372(2) \text{ \AA}$. The displacement of the Ag atom is slightly
158 anisotropic with the general direction of vibration perpendicular to an plane formed
159 approximately by four symmetrically related O1 atoms and assumes a pear-like shape (Fig.
160 6).

161

162 **Related minerals and structures**

163 The structure of theuerdankite is isotypic to that of synthetic Ag_3PO_4 (Ng *et al.*, 1978)
164 and synthetic Ag_3AsO_4 (Weil, 2003). The electronic structure of the synthetic analog of
165 theuerdankite has been investigated (e.g. Reunchan *et al.*, 2016; Li and Chen, 2017) due to its
166 promising photocatalytic properties.

167 As a chemically related mineral, tetragonal tillmannsite, $(\text{Ag}_3\text{Hg})(\text{V,As})\text{O}_4$ (Sarp *et al.*,
168 2003) could be considered. However, theuerdankite is structurally wholly distinctive.
169 Also, cubic rudabanyaite, $(\text{Ag}_2\text{Hg}_2)(\text{AsO}_4)\text{Cl}$ (Effenberger *et al.*, 2019) can be viewed as a
170 related mineral species but is structurally different.

171

172 **Discussion**

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174 *Harmonic vs. anharmonic refinement and adequate data handling*

175 Initially, the structure of theuerdankite was refined using a harmonic approach to the
176 displacement parameters of all atoms, thus described by the thermal ellipsoids. The final
177 refinement converged smoothly (including isotropic extinction and inversion twin) to
178 somewhat acceptable R -factors (comparison of harmonic and anharmonic refinement given in
179 Table 4). However, one may suggest that the goodness-of-fit (GoF) from the harmonic
180 refinement (GoF = 2.83 for all reflections) is rather high for a correct model and a reliable
181 refinement. Nevertheless, these issues warrant further discussion. The standard approach to
182 the goodness-of-fit and, consequently, a weighting scheme for the refinement is somewhat
183 misleadingly applied by many users. The most widely used program for the structure
184 refinement from the single-crystal X-ray data, SHELXL (Sheldrick, 2008), forces (if not
185 changed by the user) the refinement to achieve a GoF value close to unity, namely by
186 changing (refining) the weights. In contrast to this approach, the program Jana2020 (Petříček
187 *et al.*, 2023) does not refine the weighting scheme but bases it purely on the experimental
188 expectations (see `_refine_ls_weighting_details` in the CIF) that does not force GoF to be one.
189 Therefore, in general, the GoF values obtained by Jana are usually larger than most of those
190 reported by the SHELX program. The GoF values in Jana, however, do have a physical
191 meaning. For example, if the final reported GoF is >2.0 , it does not automatically mean that
192 the model is incorrect or entirely wrong. It just means that there are some features within a
193 given dataset that the current model 1) does not describe/fit data well enough, or 2) there are
194 systematic errors inherent to the diffraction data (from the measurement). Such undescribed
195 features can include disorder (both positional or occupational), hidden twinning, modulation,
196 or deformation of electron density (charge-density studies). Therefore, this approach also
197 requires a careful and meaningful handling and evaluation of the diffraction data. In Jana,
198 there are several ways of data handling, including different schemes and approaches to
199 averaging the reflection file for refinement (for details, see Petříček *et al.* 2014, 2023). Here,
200 we used the refinement file obtained by averaging measured reflections using Poisson
201 statistics. We used a refined instability factor value (= 0.010409), close to the most typical
202 value of instability factor tested over the years of the Jana program development, which is
203 0.01 for the “non problematic” datasets. The actual value of the instability factor for the given
204 diffraction dataset is deduced during the merging of reflections. The instability factor corrects
205 the sigma values of individual/merged reflections obtained from the file provided by the
206 diffractometer/data reduction program, such as they are fitted to the values obtained from
207 merging statistics (Poisson). We recommend using the refined value of the instability factor
208 for highly redundant datasets with reliable merging statistics. For comparison, we present here
209 difference-Fourier maps obtained from the harmonic refinements with different weights
210 (Figure 5a-c). It is apparent how the choice of the “proper” weights affects the results of the
211 refinement (and in the worst case, the wrong choice of the weights can lead to biased
212 refinement and interpretation). Finally, we relied on a refined value of the instability factor
213 (corresponding map displayed in Figure 5b) and used it for the final refinement of the
214 structure with an anharmonic approach to the atomic displacement parameters of silver (using
215 a Gram-Charlier development). The final refinement converged to $R_1 = 1.69\%$ for 519
216 observed reflections and GoF of 1.54. The final difference-Fourier map is provided in Figure
217 6a; the highest residual density is located around the silver atom (Figure 6b). For comparison,
218 the refinement with instability coefficient = 0.08 (overestimated!) would lead, in case of

219 anharmonic refinement, to $R_1 = 2.31\%$ for 519 observed reflections and a (alarming!)
220 goodness-of-fit = 0.76 with corresponding difference-Fourier electron density of 0.56 and –
221 $0.6 \text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^3$.

222 Silver atoms seem to vibrate somewhat anharmonically (Figure 7) in the theuerdankite
223 structure at room temperature, based on currently obtained high-resolution X-ray diffraction
224 data. Investigating the silver behavior as a function of temperature would be thus very
225 interesting. Nevertheless, this is beyond the scope of this paper and shall be subject to further
226 studies.

227

228 *The conditions of formation*

229 The assemblage of native silver, chlorargyrite, calcite, and theuerdankite provides only
230 limited clues about the conditions of the formation of the new mineral. Assuming that these
231 minerals formed together, the presence of silver and chlorargyrite suggests that the redox
232 conditions were near the Ag^0/Ag^+ redox boundary. The presence of calcite suggests that the
233 solutions were near-neutral.

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235 Since chlorargyrite is a fairly common secondary silver mineral, it can be asked if
236 theuerdankite is indeed rare or if it is simply overlooked. In the absence of arsenates other
237 than theuerdankite, no information about the activity of As(V) species in the aqueous solution
238 can be extracted. The solubility of Ca arsenates (e.g., haidingerite) is too high and they are not
239 a part of the observed mineral assemblage.

240

241 Thermodynamic properties of the synthetic Ag_3AsO_4 are known. Wagman et al. (1982) list
242 $\Delta_f G^\circ = -542.6 \text{ kJ/mol}$ without references to the original source. Using the appropriate
243 auxiliary data, the solubility constant $\log K_{\text{sp}}$ for Ag_3AsO_4 is

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247 Wagman et al. (1982) also provide $\Delta_f G^\circ$ values for Ag_3PO_4 , Ag_2SO_4 , and AgCl . Inserting all
248 these data into the thermodynamic database of the PHREEQC code (Parkhurst and Appelo
249 1999), some information can be extracted from available data on mine-drainage (MD) waters.
250 Because Ag is rarely analyzed, only 20 analyses from almost 1200 analyses in our collection
251 of MD waters yielded saturation indices for the Ag phases. The Fig. 8a shows that the
252 saturation indices (SI) for theuerdankite are consistently much lower than those of
253 chlorargyrite. The difference is caused by the abundance of Cl^- as an anion in most waters. In
254 fact, it is interesting that the SI values for chlorargyrite scatter around 0, meaning that this
255 mineral controls Ag concentrations in the oxidized portions of ore bodies. From these limited
256 data, it seems that theuerdankite can form only if the solutions initially contain Ag in excess
257 of Cl (in molar proportions), such that the Cl concentrations are significantly depressed by the
258 precipitation of AgCl . Hence, theuerdankite can be expected in secondary ores with abundant
259 chlorargyrite and with some source of arsenate. Reduction of Ag^+ from the solution and
260 precipitation of secondary native silver will not favor the formation of theuerdankite because
261 it removes Ag, not Cl, from the solution.

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Calculation of the saturation indices of the other phases (Fig. 8b) shows that the occurrence of Ag_3PO_4 is even less probable than that of Ag_3AsO_4 . The saturation indices are even lower, and such a potentially new mineral could only form in environments rich in chlorargyrite but unusually poor in arsenate. On the other hand, the saturation indices of Ag_2SO_4 are quite high but the availability of sulfate can be easily limited by precipitation of common secondary sulfates such as gypsum.

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Supplementary material. The supplementary material for this article can be found at

Competing interests. The authors declare none.

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356

357 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

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360 **Figure 1.** Theuerdankite (1) from the type locality associated with native silver (2) and
361 chlorargyrite (3) in the cavity of strongly supergene-weathered material; FOV 3.6 mm; photo
362 M. Gross.

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Figure 2. Dark-red internal reflections in theuerdankite visible especially around fractures and inclusions of native silver (white); field of view 700 μm; photo in reflected light (partly crossed polars) by J. Sejkora.

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Figure 3. Reflectivity curve for theuerdankite from the Alter Theuerdank Mine, St Andreasberg.

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Figure 4. Raman spectrum of theuerdankite.

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Figure 5. Difference-Fourier maps from the crystal structure refinements of theuerdankite using distinct weights (given) and harmonic approach to the ADP of silver. Color scheme: Ag = mauve, As = green, O = red; solid lines = positive contours, dashed lines = negative contours; numbers (mauve) = highest electron density ($e^{-}/\text{\AA}^3$). **A)** Refinement relying on statistics only returned a rather “noisy” difference map with too many features. **B)** Refinement using a refined value of the instability factor provides a less noisy and more “useful” difference Fourier map. **C)** Refinement with overestimated weights returns unrealistically “nearly clean” Fourier map and, accordingly, a low value of GOF. The selected weights for the final refinement were those used in **b**).

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 391 **Figure 6.** Difference-Fourier map from the final refinement of theuerdankite structure using
 392 an anharmonic approach to the ADP of silver. The color scheme is the same as in the previous
 393 figure; the highest electron density is given in $e^{-}/\text{\AA}^3$. **A)** The Difference-Fourier map from the
 394 final refinement and **b)** its 3D representation was done in the Vesta program. Thermal
 395 ellipsoids given at the 75% probability level. Residual positive electron density is displayed in
 396 yellow color (isosurface).

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 398 **Figure 7.** Representation of the anharmonic behavior of the ADP of silver at room
 399 temperature in the crystal structure of theuerdankite as obtained from the non-harmonic
 400 refinement of the displacement parameters using *JPDF* maps.

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Figure 8. a) Saturation indices for chlorargyrite (diamonds) and theurdankite (circles) in a range of pH values in mine-drainage waters. b) Box-and-whiskers diagrams that compare saturation indices of four Ag phases in mine-drainage waters. Boxes show the first and third quartile, the horizontal line the median, and the whiskers the total data range. Data in both a) and b) calculated with PHREEQC (Parkhurst and Appelo 1999), for details see text.

410 **TABLE CAPTIONS**

411

412 **Table 1.** Reflectance data for theurdankite*.

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λ (nm)	<i>R</i> (%)	λ (nm)	<i>R</i> (%)
400	14.9	560	12.7
420	14.3	580	12.7
440	13.8	589	12.7
460	13.4	600	12.7
470	13.3	620	12.7
480	13.2	640	12.6
500	13.0	650	12.5
520	12.9	660	12.5
540	12.7	680	12.4
546	12.8	700	12.4

414 *The reference wavelengths required by the Commission on Ore Mineralogy (COM) are
 415 given in bold.

416

417 **Table 2.** Chemical composition (wt.%) of theurdankite.

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Constituent	Mean	Range	S.D. (σ).
Ag ₂ O	75.22	74.64–6.19	0.46
CuO	0.03	0–0.25	0.08
As ₂ O ₅	24.80	24.22–25.45	0.35
P ₂ O ₅	0.04	0–0.23	0.08
Total	100.09		

419 S.D. - standard deviation

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422 **Table 3.** X-ray powder diffraction data (d in Å) for theuerdankite; the six strongest
423 diffractions are reported in bold.
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$I_{obs.}$	$d_{obs.}$	$d_{calc.}$	$*I_{calc.}$	$*d_{calc.}$	h	k	l
1.9	4.3338	4.3450	0.5	4.3445	1	1	0
22.9	3.0736	3.0724	17.0	3.0720	2	0	0
100.0	2.7502	2.7480	100.0	2.7477	2	1	0
55.0	2.5106	2.5086	54.1	2.5083	2	1	1
3.2	1.9438	1.9431	3.4	1.9429	3	1	0
11.1	1.7744	1.7738	13.7	1.7736	2	2	2
35.7	1.7050	1.7043	25.8	1.7040	3	2	0
43.6	1.6429	1.6423	37.8	1.6421	3	2	1
12.1	1.5370	1.5362	13.3	1.5360	4	0	0
			0.8	1.4482	4	1	1
10.9	1.3746	1.3740	10.9	1.3738	4	2	0
16.9	1.3412	1.3409	23.8	1.3407	4	2	1
7.2	1.3103	1.3101	6.5	1.3099	3	3	2
13.5	1.1413	1.1411	6.9	1.1409	5	2	0
		1.1411	13.7	1.1409	4	3	2
8.5	1.1217	1.1219	9.5	1.1217	5	2	1
8.0	1.0861	1.0863	10.9	1.0861	4	4	0
3.6	1.0240	1.0241	1.3	1.0240	6	0	0
		1.0241	3.2	1.0240	4	4	2
1.2	1.0102	1.0102	4.5	1.0101	6	1	0
6.0	0.9967	0.9968	6.5	0.9967	5	3	2
		0.9968	3.5	0.9967	6	1	1
0.3	0.9262	0.9264	4.1	0.9262	6	2	2
4.6	0.9159	0.9160	6.3	0.9159	5	4	2
		0.9160	3.1	0.9159	6	3	0
1.9	0.9060	0.9060	3.4	0.9059	6	3	1
0.9	0.8872	0.8869	3.0	0.8868	4	4	4
2.1	0.8517	0.8521	1.3	0.8520	6	4	0
1.0	0.8440	0.8441	2.3	0.8439	7	2	0
		0.8441	4.7	0.8439	6	4	1
3.2	0.8361	0.8362	3.0	0.8361	7	2	1
		0.8362	1.6	0.8361	5	5	2
		0.8362	2.3	0.8361	6	3	3
1.9	0.7870	0.7868	3.6	0.7867	6	4	3
		0.7868	1.8	0.7867	6	5	0
1.0	0.7802	0.7804	2.6	0.7803	6	5	1
		0.7804	2.7	0.7803	7	3	2

425 $*I_{calc.}$; $*d_{calc.}$ - Intensity and d_{hkl} (in Å) calculated using the software *PowderCell2.3* (Kraus
426 and Nolze, 1996) on the basis of the structural model given in Tables 4 and 5. Only
427 reflections with $I_{calc} > 0.5$ are listed.

428 **Table 4.** Summary of data collection and refinements (harmonic/anharmonic) for theuerdankite.

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	Harmonic	Cubic	Anharmonic
Crystal system		Cubic	
Space group		$P-43n$	
Unit-cell parameter a [Å]		6.132(2)	
Unit-cell volume [Å ³]		230.59(13)	
Z		2	
Calculated density [g/cm ³]	6.661 (for the formula from the structure)		
Crystal size [mm]		$0.085 \times 0.048 \times 0.028$	
Diffractometer	Rigaku XtalLab Synergy, DW system with HyPix Arc150 detector		
Temperature [K]		298	
Radiation, wavelength [Å]		MoK α , 0.71073	
θ range for data collection [°]		4.70–62.67	
Limiting Miller indices		$h = -15 \rightarrow 14, k = -14 \rightarrow 11, l = -15 \rightarrow 14$	
Axis, frame width (°), time per frame (s)		$\omega, 0.5, 5$	
Total reflections collected		4276	
Unique reflections		634	
Unique observed reflections, criterion		519, [$I > 3\sigma(I)$]	
Absorption coefficient [mm ⁻¹], type		19.63; multi-scan	
T_{\min}/T_{\max}		0.552/1	
Data completeness to θ_{\max} (%), redundancy, R_{int}		100, 6.744, 0.015	
Structure refinement	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2 by Jana2020		
No. of param., restraints, constraints	9, 0, 0		11, 0, 0
R_1, wR_2 (obs)	0.0296, 0.0965		0.0169, 0.0568
R_1, wR_2 (all)	0.0384, 0.0978		0.0226, 0.0580
GOF obs/all	2.60, 2.83		1.54, 1.66
Weighting scheme, weights	$\sigma, w = 1/[(\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.020818P)^2), P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3]$		$\sigma, w = 1/[(\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.020818P)^2), P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3]$
Extinction coefficient	370(60)		370(40)

Largest diffraction peak and hole (e^- $/\text{\AA}^3$)	2.89, -1.75	0.96, -1.08
Flack parameter; Friedel pairs	0.06(3)	0.038(17); 264

430 **Table 5.** Atom positions, equivalent displacement parameters (in Å²) and bond-valence sums
 431 (*BVS*; in valence units) for theurdankite.

432

Atom	Wyckoff	<i>x/a</i>	<i>y/b</i>	<i>z/c</i>	<i>U</i> _{eq}	<i>BVS</i>
Ag	6 <i>c</i>	1	0.25	0.5	0.02964(5)	1.059(2)
As	2 <i>a</i>	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.01133(3)	4.910(7)
O	8 <i>e</i>	0.65952(11)	0.34048(11)	0.34048(11)	0.0184(12)	2.022(4)

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436 **Table 6.** Anisotropic displacement parameters (in Å²) for atoms in theurdankite structure.

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Atom	<i>U</i> ¹¹	<i>U</i> ²²	<i>U</i> ³³	<i>U</i> ¹²	<i>U</i> ¹³	<i>U</i> ²³
Ag1	0.01916(6)	0.05058(11)	0.01916(6)	0	0	0
As1	0.01133(5)	0.01133(5)	0.01133(5)	0	0	0
O1	0.0181(2)	0.0181(2)	0.0181(2)	0.0033(2)	0.0033(2)	-0.0033(2)

438

439 **Table 7.** Selected interatomic distances (in Å) in theuerdankite.

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Ag–Ag	3.066(2) (2×)
Ag–Ag	3.7522(17) (8×)
Ag–O	2.3715(18) (4×)
Ag–O	3.4092(14) (4×)
As–O	1.6943(9) (4×)
O–O	2.7668(16) (3×)
O–O	3.444(3) (6×)

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